

Domestic Tourism Destination Preferences of Indian Youth

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In the last decade youth travel has witnessed huge growth and has been established as a specialized niche segment. India has majority of young population, which makes it important to know about the domestic tourism destinations preferred by the youth. This study focuses on the factors influencing the youths' tourist destination selection. The purpose of the study is to help tourism industry people in identifying the preferred destinations for young travelers and offering them holiday packages.

Keywords: Tourism, Domestic, SPSS, India, Economy

TOURISM has emerged as a major contributor to the economy of a nation as many new destinations have opened up and investment in tourism development resulted in socio-economic progress, job creation and infrastructure development. For many countries tourism is the major source of foreign exchange income and employment; and responsible for development. According to UNWTO, 2010 report tourism contributes 5 % to economic activities across the world.

Youth tourism has got the status of a specialized segment and more and more young people are travelling for their vacation, visiting friends and relatives, for business, religious purpose and many other reasons (UNWTO, 2010). It shows that youth travel market is growing and has good future prospects (Kale, McIntyre and Wier, 1997; Reisinger and Mavando, 2005). In such a scenario India has a variety of products to offer which can be religious tourism (Tripathi et al., 2010) eco-tourism, adventure tourism medical tourism etc. Internationally India is famous for its culture and after that medical tourism is on the verge (A study of problems and challenges faced by medical tourists visiting India, 2011). India is endowed with natural beauty and cultural heritage which attracts not only inbound tourism but also domestic tourists.

India is promoted as tourist destination by central government as well as different states are also promoting themselves to attract tourists within the country. The preference for the destination and motive behind the visit are very important in determining the tourism activity whether they are international or domestic tourists; they want their needs to be fulfilled during their visit. Tourism marketers emphasize on the various tourism product offerings and market segments to which they can offer their products.

The purpose of this study is to find the potential target market of youth tourism in India and identifying different factors influencing their choice of tourism destination.

Methodology

This study sought to address two major research questions. First, the domestic

tourism destination preferences of youth in India. Second, the factors influencing their choice of tourism destination.

Participants: The sample consists of 120 B.Tech students randomly selected from Jaypee University of Information Technology, Waknaghat. Out of 120 students 65 (54.2%) were females and 55(45.8%) were males.

Procedure: Participants were administered a questionnaire developed by the investigator to identify the domestic destination preferences and factors influencing their choice of tourism destination and the main attraction attributes of the destination. SPSS 16.0 version has been used in the data analysis. Frequency distribution and cross-tabulation and multiple response cross-tabulation have been done to achieve the objectives of the study.

Results

Descriptive statistics

Table 1: Demographics of the Students

Socio-Demographics	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	55	45.8
Female	65	54.2
Family Income		
20,000 -40,000	9	7.5
40,001-60,000	18	15
60,001-80,000	24	20
Above 80,000	69	57.5
Education		
B. Tech 1st year	30	25
B. Tech 2 nd year	30	25
B. Tech 3 rd year	30	25
B. Tech 4 th year	30	25

Table 2: Type of Destination Preferred

Type	Percentage
Adventure	74.6
Religion	12.3
Business	4.3
Education	8.7

Figure 1: Type of Destination Preferred

This was a multi response question in which one respondent might have preferred more than one type of destination. The results given in table 2 show that adventure

type of destination is most preferred by 74.6% followed by religious 12.3%, educational 8.7% and business destination was least preferred by 4.3%.

Table 3: Preferred Destination in India

Destination	Percentage
Andaman & Nicobar	1.7
Bangluru	1.7
Dharamshala	1.7
Goa	34.2
ISRO	2.5
Jammu & Kashmir	5.8
Kerala	11.7

Figure 2: Preferred Destination in India

This was a multi response question in which one respondent might have given more than one preference of destination. The results presented in table 2 shows that Goa is most preferred destination of 34.2% youth, after that Kerala was preferred by 11.7% students and Jammu & Kashmir was at the 3rd place among the preferred destinations. It means that scenic beauty influences their choice of tourism destination.

Table 4: Source of Information

Source	Percentage
Family	32.9
Friends	40.9
Internet	12.8
News/ Movies	13.4

Figure 3: Source of Information

The results presented in Table 4 indicate that the youth are highly influenced by their friends and family. Friends 40.9% and family 33% play an important role while

they are making their destination choice to visit. After friends and family internet and news/movies have same influence approximately 13% on their choice making.

Table 5: Preference for Booking

Mode	Percentage
Online Booking	62.6
Travel Agent	11.4
Manual Booking	26

Figure 4: Preference for Booking

Table 5 reflects that young tourists' most preferred mode of booking is online booking 62.6% , 26% preferred travel agents and 11.4% go for manual booking. It means that youth prefer internet for their bookings.

Table 5: Preference for Mode of Transportation

Mode of Transportation	Percentage
Air	33.3
Railway	17.6
Bus	3.3
Water	7.2
Private Vehicle	38.6

Figure 4: Preference for Mode of Transportation

The most preferred mode of transportation as shown in table 5 is private vehicle 38.6% and air travel 34% after that train 18%. Least preferred mode of travelling is water 7.2% and bus 3.3%. It means that young people prefer to travel by private vehicle.

Table 6: Tour Planning

Tour Plan	Percentage
Tour Package	16.7
Self-Organized	83.3

Figure 5: Tour Planning

Table 6 shows that 83.3% youngsters prefer self organized tours while 16.7% prefer availing the benefits of the tourism packages.

Table 7: Main Attractions

Attraction	Percentage
Scenic Beauty	23.1
Sea Beach	23.7
Shopping	8.3
Hill Station	12.2
Historical Monuments	7.4
Climate	10.1
Adventure	14.4

Figure 6: Main Attractions

As the majority of respondents would like to visit Goa so the pattern is justified that the sea beaches and scenic beauty are the main factors of attraction to visit a destination. Adventure as a first priority is chosen by 14.4% respondents, 12.2% opted for mountains, 10.1% for climate; 8.3 % for shopping and only 7.4% for historical monuments. Under the gender cross tabulation female respondents liked mountains as a greater attraction factor than the male respondents where as male respondents have greater inclination towards shopping.

Table 8: Duration of the Stay

Duration	Percentage
Weekend	9.2
Week	61.7
Fortnight	20.8
Month	8.3

Figure 7: Duration of the Stay

Table 8 reflects that 61.7% youngsters prefer to stay for a week at their favorite destination, 20.8% prefer to stay for 15 days, 9.2% prefers to stay for 3 days and 8.3% for a month.

Table 9: Amount spent

Amount	Percentage
Less than 20000	18.3
Up to 30000	35
Up to 40000	12.5
Up to 50000	9.2
More than 50000	25

Figure 8: Amount spent

Table 9 reflects that 35% respondents prefer to spend up to 30,000, 25% prefers to spend above 50,000. 13% want to spend 30,000 to 40,000, 9% would like to spend 40,000 to 50,000 and 18% will be spending less than 20,000 during their visit.

Conclusion

This study focused on two major research questions. First, the domestic tourism destination preferences of youth in India. The results reflect that adventure and scenic beauty are given preference while selecting a tourism destination. Second, the factors influencing their choice of tourism destination. It emerges that young tourist are influenced by friends' opinion the most and then family members for destination selection.

The tourism marketers should offer a customized tourism package for young people and should have flexibility in their offering to accommodate the customer. Internet should be the medium of communication and try to provide private transportation for travelling.

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